

Cost-Based Model for Selection of a Municipal Solid Waste Dumpsite in Owerri, Nigeria

Author's Details: Emeribe, A.C.¹, Nkwocha, E.E.² and Onwuagba, C.²

¹ Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria ² Federal University of Technology, Owerri, Nigeria

Abstract

this study has tried to select a waste dumpsite in Owerri Municipal, Imo State, Nigeria. The aim was to select an optimum waste dumpsite from two proposed sites at Irete and Egbeada at the outskirts of the town. Efforts were previously made to select one of these sites based on the results obtained from a conventional model, but result obtained was difficult to use for decision-making. The limitations of this conventional model were presented. Based on the data obtained on the existing dumpsites and collection centers and those from field surveys, a cost-based model was used in the final selection process. Results obtained from the application of this model showed that Irete dumpsite presented a lower haulage cost than Egbeada dumpsite and was therefore selected. This case shows that cost-based models can act as an arbiter in situations where the application of conventional and modern site selection models produced results that are difficult to use for decision-making.

Keywords: cost-based model, dumpsite, site selection, solid waste.

Introduction

Urbanization in Nigeria is beset by the significant problem of waste management. As towns grow, it becomes more and more difficult to find suitable sites for solid waste disposal. In the midst of this dilemma, residents litter their wastes indiscriminately along the roads, open drains, undeveloped plots and agricultural lands (Kumar, Balaram and Binod, 2017, Guerrero, Maas and Hogland, 2013) where they form breeding grounds to many disease vectors (flies, rats, cockroaches, mosquitoes, etc.). They create urban vulnerabilities such as fire hazards, odour nuisance, destroy scenic beauty and pollute surface and groundwater (Zumo and Vokna, 2014; Idu, 2015).

Indiscriminate dumping of waste on any land compromises its proper and future use. The public is increasingly becoming aware of the potential public hazards resulting from unsanitary disposal of a wide range of wastes.

One of the most important issues in sanitary landfilling is to site the waste facility in an optimum location. In some cities the number of sites to be selected increases with population, forcing a number of constraints (Yesilnacar, Suzen, Kaya and Doyuran, 2012). Landfill site selection is a step-by-step process that considers environmental, engineering and economic criteria. The more a site matches the ideal and fulfills the criteria requirements, the more suitable it is as a landfill site (Ohri, Singh, Maurya and Mishra, 2015).

Literature abound on different techniques used for the selection of waste dumpsites. Recent studies applied geospatial techniques and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) (Lucaino *et al.*, 2018; Nur *et al.*, 2017, Nwosu and Pepple, 2016), which are based on the multicriteria analysis (MCA). While Mwanza and Ohiri (2013) proposed an integrated model for site selection, Debishree and Sukha (2015) proffered a simplified multicriteria model which include rating, ranking and analytical hierarchy process (AHP) to determine criteria weights resulting to a single composite index for site assessment.

Models for site selection for waste dump sites are getting increased attention worldwide due to differences in locational characteristics and complexity in waste management systems (Koushik, Dutta and Krishna, 2014). In this study, a cost-based optimization model was used in the selection of a waste dumpsite in Owerri, Nigeria. The case is an example of the selection of waste dumpsite based on confusion arising from the application of a conventional method in the selection process. The application of an economic model was finally used to support decision-making in the selection exercise.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

i. Study Area

The study area is Owerri Municipality, located in the South-Eastern part of Nigeria (see Fig. I). It is bounded on the North-East, East, and South-East by Owerri North LGA and on the West, North West and South West by Owerri-West LGA. It has an estimated population of about 500,214 (2017 estimates), occupying a total mass of 24.88 square kilometers. The town serves as the economic and political hub of the

Fig. 1: Map showing the study area with dumpsites and collection centres

Source: Ministry of Lands, Survey and Urban Planning Owerri

South-East geopolitical zone of the country, with a lot of activities that contribute to the massive generation of waste which has to be collected and disposed of.

The topography of the town is flat and good, not only for the easy collection of wastes but also for the construction of waste disposal facilities such as landfills. The soils in the area are mainly sandy and clayey, well compacted, firm and stable with high load bearing capacity which can serve as good cover materials for landfills. Average temperature, rainfall, and humidity are 28°C, 214.4mm and 71.60, respectively which contribute to fast degradation of putrescible materials of the generated wastes. The type of vegetation predominant in the area (rain forest) affect the composition of solid waste generated.

From a predominantly agricultural area in the 1970s, the town has witnessed an upsurge in the number of economic activities which are contributing in no small way in the increase in the volume of solid waste generated.

ii. Data Collection

Data used for this study was collected from the five neighborhoods of the town – Old Owerri, Works Layout, Ikenegbu, World Bank Estate, and New Owerri, during a survey, carried out for a period of 14 days; using a sample of 80 people. The essence of the survey was to obtain data on the quantity of waste generated per day, waste generation rates, per capita waste generation using the method proposed by Masters (2006) and waste characteristics.

To determine the major components of the waste the method proffered by Rushbrook and Pugh (1999) was adopted. Data on the quantity of waste collected per day by waste collectors at the collection centers was generated through Load Count Analysis (Davis and Masten, 2004). The total number of collection trucks and the total volume of waste collected were added to estimate the quantity collected per day. The haulage cost of waste per ton per kilometer within the area was also obtained.

iii. Characteristics and quantity of Waste Generated

Table 1: Composition of Waste

Waste	Composition (%)
Food waste	61
Plastic	13
Paper	08
Bottle	06
Metal	07
Others	05
	100.0

Table 2: Characteristics of Existing Dumpsites

Name of dumpsite	Location	Area	Remarks
Njoku Sawmill	2km from the Centre (Owerri/Aba Rd) Flat land	8.1ha	43m from Otamiri River Almost, filled
Avu	4km from Owerri (Port Harcourt Rd) In a burrow pit	4.46ha	Along the road Almost filled

Table 3: Characteristics of Collection Centres

Name of centre	Location	Area	Remarks
Chukwuma Nwoha	Prefab District Flat land	2.6ha	Close to New Residential
Rotibi	Rotibi Street	2.26ha	Surrounded by New Residential buildings
IMSU	Close to Imo State University, Owerri	3.1ha	High nuisance to the University Community

Table 1 shows the characteristics of the waste in Owerri, with 61% of food waste, 13% plastic materials, 8% paper, 6% bottle, 7% metal and 5% others. Residents do not separate their waste before bringing them to the collection centers.

Tables 2 and 3 show the characteristics of the existing dumpsites and waste collection centres (see Fig. 1). The total landmass occupied by the two existing dumpsites is 12.56ha. The two sites were arbitrarily chosen; wastes are regularly dumped at them, without any cover materials and are exposed to weather conditions. The same applies to the three major waste collection centres where residents dumped their waste before they are collected and hauled to the two existing dumpsites, that are already getting filled as residential buildings are getting closer to them.

With a projected population of 500,214 (2017 estimates), the town generates more than 330 tons of waste, with a generation rate of 0.6kg per capita per day. Given the limited capacity of the existing dumpsites, it became imperative to look for future alternative dumpsite for the town.

Proposed Dumpsites and Limitations of the Conventional Site Selection Model

Two alternative dumpsites were proposed for Owerri, namely, Irete and Egbeada, located at the outskirts of the town at excluded areas used for subsistence farming by the villages which are at least 3km from the sites.

The first attempt to select a more appropriate dumpsite among the two candidate sites in 2016 applied the manual-based site selection model, that was based on ranking, and weighing of several criteria was used. The characteristics of the two sites were adequately considered. Such criteria as geology, hydrogeology, topography, soil, landuse, accessibility and other useful factors were considered. It was found out that the two sites were accessible (within 30mins of travel time), each presented favourable geological structures (absence of surface water, wells, no fault lines nor fractured geological structures). There were no major electrical transmission lines, nor sewer lines crossing the dumpsites. Residential buildings were at a distance 3km from the dumpsites, and each of the sites is located on a 60 hectares (Irete) and 65 hectares (Egbeada) area respectively, far above the 55 hectares projected for a future dumpsite in Owerri for a period of 35 years (with 15m constraint).

However, after proper analysis and ranking of these criteria, a simple additive weighting method was used in the selection process as proposed by Bagchi (2004). This was followed by evaluation of each of these alternatives using site sensitive index (SSI) ranging from 0 (least potential hazard) to 1 (highest potential hazard), which considered 24 attributes of each of the sites. The result obtained gave 0.52 for Irete dumpsite and 0.53 for Egbeada dumpsite.

Based on these results, it was difficult for the local authorities to make a decision in the selection of the optimum waste dumpsite for Owerri. The confusion arose from the fact that, despite the fact that Egbeada presents more disposable land, results of the sensitivity analysis carried out on the two sites show that Irete dumpsite prevailed over Egbeada dumpsite. This problem, therefore, prompted the application of another model, which acted as an arbiter in the selection of an optimum dumpsite for the town.

Model for the Selection of the Dumpsite

A cost-based model was evolved in the selection of the new waste dumpsite for Owerri. This model put into consideration some locational variables associated with the two candidate sites, represented as follows:

X_1 = Maximum transportation distance from the town (unit cost of haulage, ₦)

X_2 = Proximity to water resources (m)

X_3 = Demand for adjoining land (landuse, ₦/m²)

X_4 = Safe distance from public utilities (m)

With these variables, the suitability of any site for the proposed project can be expressed in a linear programming model:

$$Z = \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n X_{ij} C_{ij} \quad \text{min} \text{-----} (1)$$

Where

Z = the objective function representing the total cost of managing the site;

X_{ij} = distance of haulage from i th waste location to j th dumpsite, and

C_{ij} = unit cost of haulage from i th waste generation/collection point to j th dumpsite

Testing the Model

In testing the model for the selection of the optimum site, the two candidate sites at Irete and Egbeada were considered alongside the two existing ones at Avu and Njoku Sawmill whose capacities were 8540m³ and 3660m³ respectively. Also, the capacities of the waste collection centres at Chukwuma Nwoha (4000m³), IMSU (4700m³) and Rotibi (4000m³) were considered. Given that the quantities of waste from these collection centres were in excess of the capacities of the two existing dumpsites (Avu and Njoku Sawmill) determine the minimum haulage cost of selecting another dumpsite to be located either at Irete or Egbeada sites with the necessary haulage costs as presented in Table 4.

Using the notation above, the objective function could then be expressed as:

$$Z_{mn} = C_{11}X_{11} + C_{12}X_{12} + C_{13}X_{13} + C_{21}X_{21} \dots C_m X_m \dots \quad (6)$$

Where C_{ij} , C_{ij} are units costs of transportation from i th to j th locations and X_{ij} the respective distribution of waste among points i th generation points to j th dumpsite.

Cost of Selecting the Irete Dumpsite

Substituting with the results from the field survey for the Irete waste dumpsite:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{11} + X_{12} + X_{13} &= 4000m^3 \text{ for Chukwuma Nwoha} \\ X_{21} + X_{22} + X_{23} &= 4780m^3 \text{ for IMSU} \\ X_{31} + X_{32} + X_{33} &= 4000m^3 \text{ for Rotibi} \end{aligned}$$

While evacuation constraints are:

$$\begin{aligned} X_{11} + X_{12} + X_{13} &= 3660m^3 \text{ for Avu} \\ X_{12} + X_{22} + X_{32} &= 8540m^3 \text{ for Njoku Sawmill} \\ X_{13} + X_{23} + X_{33} &= 580m^3 \text{ for Irete} \end{aligned}$$

All the three iterations to Avu, Njoku Sawmill and Irete put together gave the overall situation as shown in Table 6.

Table 6: Final Iteration of total waste Generated and Evacuated (m³) to Irete Dumpsite

To \ From	Avu	Njoku Sawmill	Irete	Total generated	
Chukwuma Nwoha	3660	340	5	8	4000
IMSU	3	4780	2	7	4780
Rotibi	11	3420	6	6	4000
Total Evacuation	3,660	8,540	580		12,780

The quantity of waste generated that accumulated at Chukwuma Nwoha collection centre was evacuated to Avu and Njoku Sawmill dumpsites in the proportion of 3660m³ and 340m³ respectively, with a total waste generation of 4000m³. For the second row, the total waste generation at IMSU centre was 4780m³ while that of Rotibi to Avu, and Njoku Sawmill was 4000m³.

The cost of this distribution of solid waste for the Irete dumpsite was calculated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} C_{11}X_{11} &= \text{N}3000 \times \text{N}3600 &= \text{N}10,800,000 \\ C_{22}X_{12} &= \text{N}5000 \times 340 &= \text{N}1,700,000 \\ C_{22}X_{22} &= \text{N}2000 \times 4780 &= \text{N}9,560,000 \\ C_{32}X_{32} &= \text{N}5,000 \times 3420 &= \text{N}17,100,000 \\ C_{33}X_{33} &= \text{N}6,000 \times 580 &= \text{N}3,480,000 \\ \hline \text{Total} & &= \text{N}42,640,000 \end{aligned}$$

The amount ~~N42,640,000~~ was the total transportation cost involved in considering the first option of selecting the Irete dumpsite.

Cost of Selecting Egbeada Dumpsite

The consideration of selecting the second candidate site at Egbeada followed the same sequence as in the case of Irete. The overall iterations from Chukwuma Nwoha, IMSU and Rotibi collection centres to Avu, Njoku Sawmill and Egbeada dumpsites are presented as follows:

Table 7: Final Iteration of Total Waste Generated and Evacuated (m³) to Egbeada dumpsite

To \ From	Avu	Njoku Sawmill	Egbeada	Total generated (m ³)	
Chukwuma Nwoha	3660	340	5	7	4000
IMSU	6	4780	2	3	4780
Rotibi	11	3420	6	8	4000
Total Evacuation	3,660	8,540	580		12,780

The total cost for the distribution of solid waste for Egbeada dumpsite was calculated as follows:

$C_{11}X_{11}$	=	$\text{N}3000 \times \text{N}3600$	=	$\text{N}10,800,000$
$C_{22}X_{12}$	=	$\text{N}5000 \times 340$	=	$\text{N}1,700,000$
$C_{22}X_{22}$	=	$\text{N}2000 \times 4780$	=	$\text{N}9,560,000$
$C_{32}X_{32}$	=	$\text{N}6000 \times 3420$	=	$\text{N}20,520,000$
$C_{33}X_{33}$	=	$\text{N}8000 \times 580$	=	$\text{N}4,640,000$
Total			=	$\text{N}47,220,000$

The total transportation cost involved in considering the second option of Egbeada dumpsite was $\text{N}47,220,000$.

The result of testing the model using data collected from the generation and collection points showed that the total transportation cost to Irete dumpsite was $\text{N}42,640,000$ while that of Egbeada was $\text{N}47,220,000$.

In terms of cost, Irete dumpsite was ranked first while Egbeada dumpsite was ranked second. Therefore, it is comparatively economical in terms of transportation cost of hauling the waste to select Irete dumpsite as the optimum waste dumpsite for Owerri town. This result goes to clearly confirm the earlier result obtained from the application of the conventional model.

Discussion

Solid waste management in Owerri is bedeviled with a lot of problems in the past decade. While waste generation continues to increase, per capita waste generation has rather doubled within the period (Onwujariri, 2017). These observed trends were as a result of several factors including an increase in population and standard of living, increase in the activities of the informal sector, increased relations between the town and its hinterland, etc. (Nkwocha and Okeoma, 2009).

Despite the volumetric increase in quantity and diversity of waste generated, the town is characterized by inefficient collection methods, insufficient coverage of the collection system and improper disposal of municipal solid waste (Nzeadibe, Uyadiuno, and Akukwe, 2010). These have increased the problem of fly-tipping in open drains, undeveloped plots and the rise in the number of small unauthorized waste dumps especially at the outskirts of the town.

In response to these problems, the government of Imo State adopted a multilevel strategy by creating so many agencies responsible for solid waste management (Imo State Environmental Protection Agency (ISEPA); Imo State Sanitation Agency (ISESA); Environmental Transformation Company, ENTRACO, etc), all these without meaningful results due to poor governance and corruption.

The present administration with its Rescue Mission has therefore tried to engage meaningfully in waste management by increasing community participation and enacting bylaws and regulations in the sector. The tremendous spatial growth of the town, inadequacies of the existing dumpsites, increase in fly-tipping and street littering has prompted the government to search for a permanent dumpsite for disposal of solid waste generated in Owerri Municipality. The application of the cost-based linear programming model, which integrated cost and performance measurements as evaluation criteria, has facilitated the analysis for site selection for waste disposal in the area as well as decision-making (Li and Huang, 2010). The benefits of the model have been assessed in terms of minimizing haulage costs and distance in the process of waste dumpsite selection in the area (Cost *et al.*, 2004). Results show that this waste management model can be useful at different levels, especially to support strategic decisions, by municipalities for waste management planning and for policy decisions of governments (Mwanza and Phiri, 2013).

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study has tried to resolve the problem of selecting an optimum waste dumpsite for Owerri Municipal. An attempt made in 2016 to carry out the exercise with the application of a conventional model, produced very tight and confusing results that made the dumpsite selection process difficult for decision makers. Based on the limitations of this conventional model, a cost-based linear programming model was used to resolve the problem. This model took into account haulage costs and distance from existing dumpsites and collection centres and other important criteria in the selection process.

The case of Owerri demonstrates the fact that when results ensuing from the application of conventional and modern models on site selection process are doubtful, the use of economic models can act as an arbiter in the selection of an optimum waste dumpsite in an area.

Acknowledgments

We wish to acknowledge the immeasurable contributions of our final students in the departments of Urban and Regional Planning, Federal University of Technology, Owerri and Quantity Surveying, Imo State University, Owerri especially in data collection in the course of this study.

References

- i. Bagchi, A. (2004) *Design of landfills and Integrated Solid Waste Management (3rd Ed)*. New York: John Wiley and Sons.
- ii. Costi, P., Municiardi, R., Robba, M., Rovatti, M. and Sacile, R. (2004). *An environmental sustainable model for urban solid waste management*, *Waste Management*; 24, 277-295.
- iii. Davis, M.L. and Masters, S.J. (2004) *Principles of Environmental Engineering and Science*. New York. McGraw Hill Higher Education.
- iv. Debishree, K. and Sukha, R.S. (2015) *A Simplified Multi-criteria evaluation for*
 - a. *landfill site ranking and selection based on AHP and GIS*. *Journal of Environmental Engineering and Landscape*, 23(4) 36-41.
- v. Guerrero, L.A., Maas, G., Hogland, W. (2013) *Solid Waste Challenges for cities in*
 - a. *developing countries*. *Waste Management*, 33, 220 -232.
- vi. Idu, J.A. (2015) *Threats to Water resources development in Nigeria*. *Journal of*
 - a. *Geology and Geophysics*. 4(3), doi.org/104172/jgg.1000205.
- vii. Koushik, P., Dutta, A., and Krishna, A.P. (2014). *A Comprehensive study on landfill*
 - a. *site selection for Kolkata City, India*. *Journal of Air and Waste Management Association*; 64(7); 846-861.
- viii. Kumar, B., Balaram, P., Binod, K.C. (2017). *An analysis of Households' demand for*
 - a. *improved solid waste management in Birendranagar Municipality, Nepal*. *International Journal of Energy Economics Policy*, 7(4): 83-89.
- ix. Li, Y.P. and Huang, G. (2010). *Modeling Municipal Solid Waste Management*
 - a. *System*. *Journal of Air and Waste Management* 60, 442.
- x. Luciano, M.G.S., Giannotti, M., Larocca, A.P., Russo, M.A.T., Souza, N. da C. (2018). *Landfill siting based on optimization multiple decision analysis and Geographic Information System Analysis*. *Waste Management and Research SAGE Journal*, 36(11) 73-78.
- xi. Masters, G.M. (2006). *Introduction to Environmental Engineering and Science (2nd Ed)*. Prentice Hall: New Delhi.
- xii. Mwanza, B. and Phiri, A. (2013) *Design of a waste management model using*
 - a. *integrated solid waste management- A case of Bulawayo City Council*. *International Journal of Water Resources and Environmental Engineering*, 5(2); 110 -118.
- xiii. Nkwocha, E.E. and Okeoma, I.O. (2009). *Street Littering in Nigeria towns: Towards a*
 - a. *framework for sustainable urban cleanliness*. *African Research Review*, 3(6), 147-163.
- xiv. Nur Azriati M., Benjamin, A.M., Abdul-Rahman, S. (2017) *A review on criteria and decision making techniques in solving landfill site selection problem*. *Journal of Advanced Review on Scientific Research*, 37(1):14-32.
- xv. Nzeadibe, T.C., Uyadiuno, R.U. and Akukwe, T.I. (2010). *Solid Waste Governance in Owerri Urban Area, Nigeria: Problems and Prospects*. *Waste Management*; 30, 355-359.
- xvi. Nwosu, E.E. and Pepple, G.T. (2016) *Site selection and analysis of solid waste*
 - a. *dumpsites in Ile-Ife, Nigeria*. Paper presented FIG Working Week, Recovery from Disaster, Christchurch New Zealand, May 2-6, 2016.
- xvii. Ohri, A., Singh, P.K., Maurya, S. and Mishra, S. (2015). *Sanitary Landfill Site Selection using Geographic Information System*. *Proceedings of National Conference on Open Source GIS: Opportunities and Challenges*, Dept. of Civil Engineering, IIT (BHU) Varanasi, October 9-10, 2015.
- xviii. Onwujiariri, C.M. (2017). *Evolving a Time-Integrated Model for Optimization of*
 - a. *Solid Waste Management in Imo State*, Paper presented at Waste Management Conference in Owerri, 20th July 2017, Owerri, Imo State.
- xix. Rushbrook, P. and Pugh, M. (1999). *Solid waste landfills in the middle and lower*
 - a. *income countries: A technical guide for planning, design and operation*. World Bank Technical Paper. No 426, New York. The World Bank
- xx. Yesilnacar, M.I., Suzen, M.L., Kaya, B.S. and Doyuran, V. (2012) *Municipal Solid*
- xxi. *Waste landfill site selection for the city of Sanliurfa, Turkey: An example of MCDA Integrated with GIS*. *Integrated Journal of Digital Earth*, 5(2), 147-164.